

A Dataset for Supporting Power Management Experimentations in Cloud and Edge Infrastructures

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Abstract—As advancements in cloud computing, edge computing, and mobile telecommunication infrastructures continue to accelerate, concerns regarding environmental sustainability have become increasingly important. In this context, optimizing the energy efficiency of computational resources, particularly CPUs, which are major contributors to system-level power consumption becomes a key area of focus. This paper introduces a new, publicly available dataset that captures the effects of CPU P-States, C-States, and frequency Governors on power consumption and system performance. The dataset comprises 5,621 unique configurations with 337,260 samples of these CPU parameters, each tested under three distinct load conditions: idle, medium, and high. These scenarios are designed to emulate real-world usage patterns observed in cloud and edge infrastructures. By enabling in-depth analysis of performance/energy trade-offs, the dataset serves as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners aiming to develop sustainable computing solutions.

Keywords—CPU power consumption, CPU C-States, Intel P-States, CPU frequency Governors, Cloud infrastructure power-performance dataset.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability and efficient energy consumption have become critical areas of focus for infrastructure providers, academic researchers, independent developers, and hardware manufacturers. Given that servers and particularly CPUs are among the most power-hungry components in modern computing infrastructures [1], significant attention has been directed toward improving their energy efficiency. This growing emphasis reflects the urgent need to reduce the environmental impact of large-scale computing systems while maintaining high levels of performance and scalability [2].

Modern processors and Operating Systems (OS) offer several power management features at both hardware and software levels to optimize performance and energy consumption. These mechanisms allow for dynamic or manual adjustments to clock speed, voltage, and internal component states. Among them, CPU idle states (C-States) enable the processor to enter various sleep modes by disabling specific internal components, reducing power usage at the cost

of increased transition latency depending on the depth of the idle state. CPU performance states (P-States) adjust the processor’s frequency and voltage during active operation to balance performance and power efficiency. Additionally, CPU frequency Governors, defined at the kernel level, implement policies that manage frequency scaling in response to workload demands, offering different trade-offs between power savings and responsiveness [2]-[5].

Several research efforts have proposed and developed tools, frameworks, and system-level enhancements aimed at reducing power consumption by regulating CPU power management features. These approaches often focus on dynamically adjusting CPU frequency, voltage, and idle state configurations based on real-time workload characteristics, with the goal of improving energy efficiency while maintaining acceptable performance levels. However, despite these advancements [6]-[8], there remain vast opportunities for further exploration and optimization particularly through the application of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. These intelligent models have the potential to learn complex patterns in system behavior and make adaptive decisions that outperform static or rule-based strategies in dynamic environments. To this end, there is a clear lack of comprehensive datasets that capture the full range of CPU dynamic power and performance management features under realistic workload conditions. In this paper, we present a system designed to emulate various real-world CPU load scenarios and collect a complete dataset [9] that captures system behavior under a wide range of CPU power management configurations.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the fundamental concepts behind dynamic power management features. Section 3 describes the methodology used in the study, including details of the testbed system and the parameters explored in the dataset. In Section 4, we present an analysis of power consumption and performance behavior across a variety of load conditions and CPU configurations. Additionally, we highlight several potential use cases and application scenarios where this dataset can be leveraged to advance research and

development in energy-efficient computing. Section 5 concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings and insights, while also identifying promising directions for future research. It emphasizes the critical need for continued innovation in balancing performance and energy consumption to meet growing sustainability goals in computing infrastructures.

II. DYNAMIC POWER MANAGEMENT

In this section, we describe and briefly explain the key CPU and kernel-level parameters that directly influence CPU frequency, performance, and power consumption. These parameters govern the behavior of the processor’s power management mechanisms, including dynamic frequency scaling, idle state transitions, and workload scheduling, all of which play a critical role in the system’s energy-performance trade-offs.

A. CPU Idle State (C-State)

C-States (ranging from C0 to Cn) are power saving modes that a processor enters during periods of inactivity. They form a fundamental component of the dynamic power management strategies employed by modern CPUs to reduce energy consumption when full computational performance is not needed. Each successive C-State offers progressively greater power savings by disabling additional internal components of the processor. However, these deeper idle states come at the cost of increased transition latency, as returning the processor to the active state requires more time and energy. The CPU C-States and their parameters are exposed to the OS through the Advanced Configuration and Power Interface (ACPI) and model-specific registers (MSRs), enabling dynamic and efficient management of power/performance trade-offs [10]-[13]. The main characteristics of the most commonly implemented C-States are summarized in Table 1.

State	Description	Power Saving	Transition Latency
C0	Active state	None	N/A
POLL	Kernel busy wait	Minimal/None	~0 [μs]
C1-C3	Shallow sleep-Sleep	Low/Moderate	~1–80 [μs]
C4-C7	Deep sleep	Moderate/High	~80–100 [μs]
C8-Cn	Deeper package sleep	Very high	100+ [μs]

Table 1. C-State characteristics.

B. CPU Performance States (P-States)

P-States are power states that determine specific combinations of operating frequency and voltage while the CPU is actively executing instructions. These states form a core component of Intel’s Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) strategy, allowing the processor to dynamically adjust its performance and energy usage in response to real-time workload demands, thermal conditions, and system-level power management policies.

In modern Intel® processors, P-State selection is managed either by the OS or by hardware. When the *intel_pstate* driver operates in active mode, Hardware-Controlled Performance States (HWP) allow the CPU to autonomously select optimal

P-State based on OS-level policy hints such as *performance*, *balance_performance*, *balance_power*, and *power*. These transitions occur with nearly instantaneous and seamless latency, enabling rapid adaptation to workload changes. In passive mode, the OS directly controls frequency scaling using standard CPU frequency Governors [14]-[18].

C. CPU Frequency Governors

CPU frequency Governors are software components within the OS CPU frequency scaling infrastructure that dynamically adjust the processor’s operating frequency to balance power consumption and performance based on workload, power management policies, and defined minimum and maximum frequency limits. On Intel® systems using the *intel_pstate* driver in active mode, only two Governors, *performance* and *powersave* are available. However, when the *intel_pstate* driver operates in passive mode, it relies on the ACPI scaling interface (*acpi-cpufreq*), which supports the full range of standard CPU frequency Governors: *performance*, *powersave*, *ondemand*, *conservative*, *schedutil*, and *userspace*, these Governors apply different frequency regulations in order to reduce power consumption and change the performance preferences [19]-[21].

III. METHODOLOGY

This section provides a detailed description of all the features used to construct the dataset.

A. Testbed Description

To ensure consistent and reproducible results across all experimental scenarios, all tests were performed on a system with the hardware and software specifications detailed in Table 2.

Platform	Intel® NUC9VXQNX
OS	Ubuntu Server 24.04.2 LTS
CPU	Intel® Xeon® E-2286M
Total Cores	8
Total Threads	16
Base Frequency	2.40 [GHz]
Max Turbo Frequency	5.00 [GHz]
RAM	64 [GB]
Storage	1 [TB]
Power Supply	500 [W] 80+ Platinum

Table 2. Dataset platform specifications.

Regarding the monitoring tools, Intel® Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) [14] and kernel log files, which are continuously updated by the OS, were utilized to gather power and system-level metrics. Additionally, a custom Python-based benchmarking tool was employed. In each iteration, it multiplies two 300×300 matrices to keep cores busy while fitting in the CPU cache and minimizing system interference. It records the computation time with microsecond precision, providing a consistent workload to assess system performance and energy consumption under varying configurations.

Measurements were collected at a fixed interval of 1 second with each test running for 1 minute providing a representative window; shorter or longer runs reduce reliability or extend collection time without changing results.

All logs were time-synchronized and temporarily buffered in RAM in batches of 60 samples to minimize CPU overhead during data collection. The buffered data was then written to structured CSV files during the interval between consecutive configuration changes and test executions.

B. Parameters

To evaluate the power-performance trade-offs, we systematically varied key CPU parameters under different load conditions:

- **C-States:** as described in Table 1, the system supports nine distinct CPU idle states: POLL, C1, C1E, C3, C6, C7s, C8, C9, and C10. All possible combinations of these C-States were systematically enabled or disabled to evaluate their impact on power consumption and latency.
- **P-States:** the system was tested under various P-State preferences, including *performance*, *balance_power*, *balance_performance*, and *power*, depending on whether the active or passive CPU frequency scaling driver was in use. Although *default* is a selectable option, it internally corresponds to one of the other four preferences based on the system’s policy and driver behavior. Therefore, the *default* configuration was excluded from testing to avoid repetition.
- **CPU Governors:** multiple CPU frequency scaling Governors were evaluated, including *performance*, *powersave*, *ondemand*, *conservative*, *userspace*, and *schedutil*. However, the availability of Governors depends on the P-State driver mode:
 - a) *Active mode:* all abovementioned P-State preferences are available, but only two Governors, *performance* and *powersave* can be used.
 - b) *Passive mode:* disables P-State preferences and enables the full set of CPU frequency Governors.
- **Load Conditions:** experiments were conducted under three load scenarios:
 - a) *Idle:* the system was left in a near-idle state, running only essential kernel processes and the test scripts.
 - b) *Medium:* a moderate, constant load was applied, maintaining CPU utilization randomly between 40% and 50% across all cores. This was achieved using a custom workload generator that dynamically adjusts the load for each core every 100 milliseconds (one-tenth of each iteration), selecting a random utilization value within the specified range. This approach simulates typical multitasking conditions by varying loads across CPU cores over time.
 - c) *High:* all cores were stressed to maintain CPU utilization between 70% and 80%, simulating a near full-load condition. This was achieved using the same dynamic workload generation method described for the medium load scenario.

C. Data Collection

This section describes how data was gathered and structured:

- **Measurement Strategy:** metrics were collected at regular intervals of one second, with each test running for one minute, resulting in 60 iterations per configuration. For each unique parameter combination, a separate CSV file containing timeseries measurements was generated. In total, 5,621 CSV files were produced for each load condition tested, with each file corresponding to a distinct configuration representing a unique combination of C-States, P-States, and CPU Governors.
- **Collected Metrics:** the dataset includes timestamps along with various metrics collected during the experiments. These metrics include multiple power consumption domains reported by the Intel® RAPL interface. Additionally, it contains per-core frequency, per-core utilization, the CPU Governor in use, per core P-State, and enabled C-States for each core. For each core, the dataset also records the amount of time spent in each C-State. Finally, benchmark latency measurements are included to capture the system performance under each configuration.
- **Dataset Structure and Scale:** In total, 5,621 unique configurations were tested across three load conditions, generating 16,863 CSV files. The final dataset consists of 1,011,780 timeseries samples, with each row containing the abovementioned metrics. Since the first row of each file used as the baseline for subsequent metric calculations and not containing valuable information is excluded from the analysis.

IV. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND USAGE EXAMPLES

This section is divided into two parts. First, we analyze the results of the tests conducted under different load conditions, focusing on the trade-offs between power consumption, latency, and idle state configurations. Then, we explore potential application areas where this dataset can be utilized for further research and analysis.

A. Results and Analysis

To begin with, Intel® RAPL exposes power metrics for multiple power domains; however, the primary metric of interest in this study is the one corresponding to the CPU package, which reflects the overall CPU power consumption. Table 3 presents the mean values of the collected metrics.

Mean Value	Idle load	Medium load	High load
Power [W]	2.398	30.507	46.596
Frequency [MHz]	1792.003	3310.751	3896.722
CPU utilization [%]	0.489	45.425	75.298
Latency [ms]	26.846	24.633	21.492
CPU active time [%]	0.798	45.497	75.328
CPU idle time [%]	99.202	54.503	24.672

Table 3. Mean values of collected metrics.

Figure 1. Latency vs power consumption with different P-State/Governor configurations.

As expected, the mean value of power consumption under medium and high load conditions is significantly higher compared to the idle state. A similar trend is observed in the mean CPU core frequency, which aligns with the increased average CPU utilization across these load levels. However, the mean latency of the benchmark computation described in Section III.B does not exhibit a significant decrease in relation to CPU active time or utilization. Nonetheless, it varies noticeably across specific configurations, particularly with different P-State preferences and CPU Governors. The observed mean values of CPU active and idle time are consistent with expectations, as the load generator described in Section III.B is designed to operate within these ranges for medium and high load conditions.

Figure 1 provides a detailed view of the relationship between different CPU configurations P-State preferences and CPU Governors and their corresponding mean values of benchmark latency and power consumption. Each configuration is represented by 511 data points, reflecting the mean value of all metrics collected in each CSV file as described in section III.C. Figure 1.A illustrates the results under the idle load condition with P-States configured in active mode, where only two Governors are available. It can be observed that the *performance* and *balance_performance* preferences generally result in lower latency compared to *power* and *balance_power*. However, this improvement in latency often comes at the cost of higher power consumption, with several configurations showing significantly increased power usage. Notably, some configurations manage to maintain low latency while operating at relatively low power levels, indicating a more favorable latency/power trade-off under certain settings. Additionally, *balance_power* demonstrates lower latency than *power* in many scenarios,

while maintaining a similar power consumption range. Figure 1.B presents the same metrics under the medium load condition. In this case, the *balance_performance* and *performance* preferences do not produce configurations within the lower power consumption range, as observed under idle conditions, although they maintain latency in a similar range. Conversely, the *power* and *balance_power* preferences show both an increase in power consumption and a reduction in latency compared to the idle scenario, highlighting a shift in the trade-off dynamics under medium load. Figure 1.C shows the metrics under the high load condition. In this scenario, all P-State preferences tend to have reduced latency compared to idle and medium load conditions. Notably, the *power* and *balance_power* preferences achieve significantly lower latencies while maintaining power consumption levels lower than the *performance* and *balance_performance* preferences. This suggests that, under high load, power-efficient configurations can offer latency performance comparable to high-performance modes, but with improved energy efficiency.

Figure 1.D presents the results under the idle load condition with P-States configured in passive mode, where all standard CPU Governors are available. The *conservative*, *ondemand*, *performance*, and *userspace* Governors generally maintain mean latencies in the range of 12–13 ms and power consumption between 0–5 W. However, some configurations using these Governors show significantly higher power consumption while remaining within the same latency range. The *schedutil* Governor exhibits a much wider spread in latency, ranging from very low values up to approximately 46 ms, while maintaining a similar power consumption range. This variability is likely influenced by the different combinations of enabled C-States. The *powersave* Governor

Figure 2. Minimum, Mean, and Maximum values of power consumption with different number of enabled C-States.

consistently shows the highest latency among all policies, yet it does not offer any notable improvement in power consumption compared to the other Governors. Figure 1.E, which presents the same metrics under the medium load condition, shows that the *conservative*, *ondemand*, *performance*, *userspace*, and *schedutil* Governors generally fall within a similar latency range. Among them, *schedutil* shows comparatively lower power consumption and no wide spread comparing with the idle load condition, indicating better energy efficiency under this load level. On the other hand, the *powersave* Governor results in significantly higher latency not only compared to the other Governors but also relative to its own performance under idle conditions. Figure 1.F shows the same metrics under the high load condition. The *conservative*, *ondemand*, *performance*, *userspace*, and *schedutil* Governors continue to have behavior similar to that observed under medium load, keeping comparable latency values. However, their power consumption range is more narrowed, reflecting the limited room for frequency scaling under heavy workloads. In contrast, the *powersave* Governor shows even higher latency than in the previous two load conditions, while its power consumption remains nearly unchanged, indicating lower power consumption, reinforcing its energy-saving nature at the cost of responsiveness.

Figure 2 illustrates the impact of the number of enabled C-States regardless of their specific order on overall power consumption, represented by the mean, maximum, and minimum values across all P-State preferences and Governor policies. Figure 2.A shows this comparison under the idle load condition. It can be observed that when only a single C-State is enabled, power consumption varies significantly from minimum values associated with deep sleep states to maximum values corresponding to the POLL state, which represents a kernel-level busy-wait mechanism designed to maintain the lowest possible latency by keeping the CPU fully responsive. Enabling two or more C-States allows the CPU to enter deeper idle states more effectively, which consistently results in lower power consumption. Figure 2.B shows the results under the medium load condition, where both the mean and maximum power consumption values show less variation compared to the idle case. Overall power consumption is higher across all metrics mean, maximum, and minimum due to the increased system activity. Despite this, the influence of deeper C-States remains visible, as reflected in the minimum power values, which are still relatively low, although higher than those observed under idle load. Figure 2.C presents the

results under the high load condition, where all power consumption metrics mean, maximum, and minimum are higher than those observed in both idle and medium load scenarios. However, the variation across different numbers of enabled C-States is minimal, indicating that under heavy workload, the CPU remains active most of the time, limiting the influence of idle states on overall power consumption.

B. Usage Examples

The dataset offers multiple areas for exploration; here, we present a few examples of potential use cases and applications.

- ML/AI models for system optimization:** With the rapid advancements in edge and cloud computing, alongside with the growing sustainability concerns among telecom providers and infrastructure operators, there is increasing interest in optimizing both energy efficiency and system performance. This dataset offers detailed CPU behavior across a broad range of configurations including various combinations of P-States, C-States, and CPU frequency Governors under different workload intensities offers a rich foundation for developing and evaluating ML/AI models. These models can learn to identify optimal CPU configurations that minimize power consumption while keeping, and potentially even improving, system performance. Such capabilities are particularly valuable for intelligent workload scheduling, adaptive power management, and real-time optimization in resource-constrained or energy-aware environments. Furthermore, the dataset can support resource orchestration in energy-constrained cloud or edge computing nodes, where dynamic and efficient allocation is critical. It also enables the design of Service Level Agreement (SLA)-aware scheduling policies that account for power/performance trade-offs, helping systems meet latency requirements while optimizing energy usage.
- System power/performance analysis:** Studying how different workloads and CPU-related configurations affect system behavior specifically in terms of performance, frequency, utilization, and power consumption is essential for identifying inefficiencies in power management strategies at both the hardware and software levels. This dataset enables detailed

analysis of such interactions, making it valuable for identifying suboptimal configurations, evaluating the effectiveness of current mechanisms, and evaluating idle state policies. The insights derived from these analyses can guide the design of more energy-efficient architectures and system-level power management frameworks, making it a significant area of interest for both academic research and industrial development.

- **Sustainability and energy efficiency:** this dataset enables developers and companies to build auto-tuning applications that balance power consumption and performance across a wide range of devices from mobile phones and laptops to desktops and gaming systems. By dynamically adjusting CPU configurations like P-States, C-States, and Governors, these solutions can extend battery life, reduce energy costs, and support greener computing devices. This helps both individual users and small to large-scale companies improve energy efficiency while maintaining desired performance levels.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we introduced a novel dataset that captures the influence of various hardware and software CPU parameters such as P-States, C-States, and frequency Governors on system performance and power consumption. Given that CPUs are among the most power-hungry components in computing systems, understanding these relationships is essential for improving energy efficiency. We detailed the data collection methodology, provided key insights through analysis, and outlined potential use cases where this dataset can support research and development.

As part of our future work, we aim to extend this analysis to include a broader range of CPU models and architectures in realistic operational loads. Our goal is to develop intelligent ML/AI agents capable of learning and applying optimal CPU configurations that reduce power consumption while keeping, and even improving, system performance. This aligns with the broader objective of enhancing sustainability in computing systems, especially in energy-constrained environments such as data centers, edge clouds, and telecom infrastructure.

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